

A Direct Evidence for Hyperconjugation from Nuclear Overhauser Effect Study

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Nuclear Overhauser effect studies show that the higher field shift of aromatic proton (2H) in intramolecularly bonded 3-(N,N-dialkylaminomethyl)-4-hydroxyacetophenones is mainly due to a directionally favourable hyperconjugative effect.

In previous communication¹ we reported strong hydrogen bonding in 3-(N,N-dialkylaminomethyl)-4-hydroxy acetophenones (1a-c), where the 4-hydroxy group and the nitrogen atom of the 3-aminomethyl group acted as donor and acceptor respectively. From ¹H nmr study it has been found that the proton at 2-position in these compounds appeared as a broad singlet and at somewhat higher field (7.72 ppm) compared to the corresponding signals of the proton at 6-position (7.81 ppm). This higher field shift of proton signal at 2-position was not observed for the corresponding non-hydrogen bonded compound (2a), so we attributed this phenomenon arising due to hydrogen bonding. Being a hindered molecule, the free rotation of the amino methyl group was restricted resulting in a rigid cyclic structure. From structural point of view, it is quite possible that due to this rigidity the methylene protons in the cyclic hydrogen-bonded conformer orient themselves in favourable directions and the resulting favoured orientation of the methylene protons further exerts some effect on proton at 2-position of the aromatic ring during nmr relaxation time. This observation prompted us to undertake nmr nuclear Overhauser enhancement study of one such methylene compound (1c) to derive a definite conclusion whether directionality of methylene protons has any contribution on aromatic ring system.

1a, R = Me
1b, R = Et
1c, R = IsoPr

2a

tion was found to split into a doublet (J 2 Hz) with enhanced peak intensity. The splitting of the singlet with peak enhancement confirms that the methylene protons and the proton at 2-position of the aromatic ring are on the same side of the molecule^{2,3}. This enhancement was real (increase in integral) and not due to removal of long range coupling. Existence of these three protons on the same side is possible only when free rotation of the (amino)-methyl group ($-\text{CH}_2\text{NR}_2$) is inhibited by forming a rigid, planar and cyclic structure between the lone-pair orbital on the nitrogen atom of the 3-aminomethyl group and the adjacent 4-hydroxy group. Each of the two methylene protons makes *ca.* 55° angle with the aromatic plane and *ca.* 35° angle with the *p*-orbital plane of C-3 of the aromatic ring (Drieding model-basis). A 15% increase in peak intensity for proton at 6-position (*para* to the aminomethyl group) signals indicates that a electronic delocalisation in the aromatic ring is associated with the methylene protons^{4,5}. Further irradiation of the acetyl group (which should have equal weight on the down-field shift and on its electron-withdrawing capacity) for protons at 2 and 6 position at 2.54 ppm but there was a difference in peak intensity (2% and 8%)⁶ indicating that acetyl group is *S-trans* to the double bond between C-1 and C-6 of the aromatic ring^{3,6} and also the effect of adjacent methylene on proton 2 of aromatic rings.

All these observations support that a strong hyperconjugative effect is operating in the molecule which is becoming more prominent due to hydrogen bonding. In this hydrogen bonded-rigid cyclic structure the two σ -orbitals for the methylene protons exist in a very favourable position and the orbital interaction between one of these σ -orbitals and the *p*-orbital (angle between σ -orbital and *p*-orbital is *ca.* 35°) of C-3 of the aromatic ring partially influence the two-position^{7,8} of aromatic ring resulting an increase in electronic charge and shielding of proton at 2-position compared to 6 (proton) of aromatic ring⁹. The observed enhancement of peak for the proton at 6-position of aromatic ring is clear indication that a

On irradiating the methylene protons at 3.93 ppm, the broad singlet due to proton at 2-posi-

hyperconjugative effect is operating in the molecule and enabling the title compound to exist in a composite of the possible conformers *A*, *B*, *C* and *D* (Scheme 1), among which *B* seems to be the major contributor to nmr time-scale.

Scheme 1

It can now be summarised that the nmr spectra on the studied molecules lead to a probable non-bonded interaction¹⁰ which could be hyperconjugative in nature.

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